

**Levels and air-sea
exchange of POPs in the
marginal sea of Europe:
contribution to the global
monitoring effort
AQUA-GAPS/MONET**

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Introduction

Many man-made chemicals are long-lived i.e., resist degradation in the environment and are globally cycling between atmosphere, ocean and other compartments. These persistent organic pollutants (POPs) have been reaching the global marine environment through atmospheric deposition and riverine sources since decades, but are not monitored and data from the open oceans are very rare. Following bans, hence, decline of the concentration in air or seasonal variation, the direction of air-sea exchange may reverse in relaxation to chemical equilibrium and turn seas into secondary sources of the pollutant (Lammel et al., 2015, 2016). Moreover, in recent decades additional contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) have been reaching the Mediterranean marine environment (Brumovsky et al., 2017) which is of paramount importance, given the oceans are a key sink for pollutants, a habitat for wildlife and a global source of food supply. Our simultaneous monitoring in surface water and air provides insights on the current state of POPs' and CECs' long-term evolutions of contamination and chemodynamics in the marine environment including determination of seasonality and identification of secondary sources.

Most of the investigated substances are semivolatile, hence exchanging between surfaces and the atmosphere (re-volatilisation, secondary sources), and long-lived, hence transported regionally (Europe and in the continental outflow) or even globally. Apart from variation of sources, season is influencing the air-sea exchange. Therefore, the study addresses the source region (Europe) and the background marine atmosphere in the region and even on global scale. This complements on-going research on source distribution and multicompartamental fate of CECs in the region (Europe).

Figure 1: Passive samplers deployed at the E1-M3A marine observatory.

Objectives

The main project objectives are: i) Determination of levels of a range of persistent and emerging organic substances in surface waters of the Mediterranean and in the atmosphere, and determination of the direction of diffusive air-sea exchange fluxes; b) Investigation of the seasonality of occurrence of the monitored substances in water and air as a basis; c) for the future long-term trend monitoring in support of the on-going global monitoring at a marine background site within the AQUAGAPS/ MONET network.

Methodology

The research was performed within the AQUA-GAPS/MONET worldwide monitoring network of aquatic organic contaminants (see the first results in Sobotka et al., 2022; Lohmann et al. 2023; Lohmann et al. 2024). The network aims to derive baseline concentrations and time-trends of various dissolved hydrophobic organic contaminants (HOCs), and other contaminants of emerging concern globally, relying on standardised passive sampling tools and a centralized sample analysis that allows for direct comparison of data while minimizing measurement uncertainty.

E1-M3A marine observatory has become a regular site for monitoring within the AQUA-GAPS/MONET network of legacy POPs in surface waters at sites with background pollution.

The work included deployment of passive water and passive air samplers in the Aegean Sea during several seasons at the E1-M3A marine observatory. Deployments included various water passive samplers (sheets of silicone for sampling neutral legacy POPs, a porous polyethylene tube sampler for sampling PFAS, and Baker Bond Speedisk samplers for polar emerging contaminants, all mounted on stainless steel holders) and passive air samplers (polyurethane foam disks in metal bowls). The samplers for four sampling events, each planned for 100 days of exposure, were shipped from RECETOX to HCMR. Samplers were exposed by HCMR at the E1-M3A buoy for three consecutive exposure periods: 1st period from 16/4/2024-3/8/2024; 2nd period from 3/8/2024-13/11/2024. The 3rd deployment period commenced on the 13/11/2024, but the samplers could not be recovered because of a physical damage of the platform. The 4th intended deployment was not performed. After exposure, HCMR sent the exposed samplers to RECETOX for chemical analysis and data interpretation. The exposed samplers were analysed by the RECETOX research infrastructure, aiming at water and air concentrations of investigated POPs and other relevant compounds, including polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDE), novel brominated flame retardants, organophosphate esters (OPE), musks, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). From the planned four consecutive sampler deployments at E1-M3A, two were successfully performed.

Sample extraction and instrumental analysis using gas or liquid chromatography/tandem mass spectrometry was performed in the RECETOX central laboratories, accredited for standard

analysis methods EN ISO/IEC 17025. The results were interpreted based on available models according to the previously published methodology to derive aqueous and air concentrations of investigated POPs and other relevant compounds, including polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organochlorine and currently used pesticides (OCPs), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDE), novel brominated flame retardants, organophosphate esters (OPE), musks, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs).

Figure 2: Deployment of passive samplers at the E1-M3A observatory by the team from Hellenic Centre for Marine Research

Results

The project intended four subsequent seasonal deployments of passive water and passive air samples in the Aegean Sea envisaged during spring, summer, autumn and at the E1-M3A marine observatory. The aim was to investigate the seasonality of aqueous and atmospheric concentrations of investigated compounds in order to select the best season for the future temporal trend monitoring in water at the E1-M3A site. This objective was fulfilled partially, by covering two subsequent seasons – spring-summer and summer-autumn 2024.

Data reported to EMSO ERIC data repositior, include the reporting template of Metadata on passive sampling of persistent and emerging organic substances in surface seawater at the E1-M3A marine observatory. The the dataset contains metadata describing the coordinates

of the sampling site, the metadata on the applied sampler types, their deployment periods, sampling protocols, detailed information about the laboratory processing including the extraction, instrumental analysis of organic micropollutants in the passive samplers, the calculation of aqueous concentrations of micropollutants from passive sampler data, QA/QC measures applied during sample processing, a database of parameters (organic compounds) that will be reported from the analysis of samples, and data obtained from sampling at E1-M3A. High quality results on including polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDE), novel brominated flame retardants, organophosphate esters (OPE), musks, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), in water were obtained by application of validated and QA/QC-assured procedures that are now routinely applied by the Trace laboratory at RECETOX. These are publicly available in the data repository, with the dataset name *EMSO_ERIC_Data on passive sampling in surface seawater at the_E1_M3A_marine observatory*.

Conclusions and Future work

Results of the work will contribute to the global monitoring effort within the AQUA-GAPS/MONET worldwide monitoring network of aquatic organic contaminants. Concentrations of detected chemicals in seawater and air at the E1-M3A station will be made publicly available with the support of RECETOX infrastructure in the GENASIS (Global ENvironmental ASsessment Information System), which provides a comprehensive information on contamination of the environment by chemicals (www.genasis.cz). The data will be used for publications in peer reviewed scientific journals, addressing the main project objectives. Results will be presented at scientific conferences including the International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment (ICCE) and the SETAC Europe annual meeting. The data will be used to support the implementation of the Stockholm Convention (SC) on POPs.

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